

C Cardiovascular pathologies and their detection at the initial therapist's examination

Patologías cardiovasculares y su detección en el examen inicial del terapeuta

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Abstract

The article considers modern approaches to the detection of cardiovascular pathologies at the stage of primary examination by a general practitioner. Cardiovascular diseases (CVD) remain the leading cause of mortality and morbidity worldwide, which emphasises the importance of their early diagnosis. The main clinical manifestations of CVD are presented, to which attention should be paid during history taking and physical examination, including patient complaints, auscultation, blood pressure and pulse measurements. For clarifying the diagnosis, particular attention is paid to initial diagnostic algorithms and the use of instrumental methods, such as ECG. The authors discuss key CVD risk factors such as hypertension, dyslipidaemia, obesity and diabetes mellitus and emphasise the importance of a preventive approach. Emphasis is placed on the role of therapist in timely referral of patients to a cardiologist for in-depth evaluation and treatment. The results of the article emphasise the need to integrate a comprehensive approach to the detection of CVDs in the practice of primary care physicians to improve the efficiency of diagnosis and reduce mortality.

Keywords: cardiovascular diseases, primary examination, therapist, early diagnosis, risk factors, arterial hypertension, ECG, prevention, auscultation, physical examination.

Resumen

El artículo considera enfoques modernos para la detección de patologías cardiovasculares en la etapa del examen primario realizado por un médico de cabecera. Las enfermedades cardiovasculares (ECV) siguen siendo la principal causa de mortalidad y morbilidad en todo el mundo, lo que subraya la importancia de su diagnóstico precoz. Se presentan las principales manifestaciones clínicas de la ECV, a las que se debe prestar atención durante la anamnesis y el examen físico, incluidas las quejas del paciente, la auscultación, la presión arterial y las mediciones del pulso. Para aclarar el diagnóstico se presta especial atención a los algoritmos de diagnóstico inicial y al uso de métodos instrumentales como el ECG. Los autores analizan los factores de riesgo clave de ECV, como la hipertensión, la dislipidemia, la obesidad y la diabetes mellitus, y enfatizan la importancia de un enfoque preventivo. Se pone énfasis en el papel del terapeuta en la derivación oportuna de pacientes a un cardiólogo para una evaluación y tratamiento en profundidad. Los resultados del artículo enfatizan la necesidad de integrar un enfoque integral de la detección de ECV en la práctica de los médicos de atención primaria para mejorar la eficiencia del diagnóstico y reducir la mortalidad.

Palabras clave: enfermedades cardiovasculares, examen primario, terapeuta, diagnóstico precoz, factores

Cardiovascular diseases (CVDs) occupy leading positions among the causes of mortality and disability of the population in the world. According to the World Health Organisation (WHO), more than 17 million people die annually from these diseases. The main factor determining unfavourable outcome remains late diagnosis due to untimely application of patients for medical help and insufficient detection of pathologies at early stages¹.

Initial examination by a therapist plays a key role in the early detection of cardiovascular disease, especially in settings with limited access to specialised care. Competent use of clinical skills, basic instrumental techniques (such as electrocardiography) and careful consideration of risk factors can significantly improve diagnostic performance.

The importance of a preventive approach and the role of the primary care physician is increasing given the growing burden on health care systems and the growing number of patients with chronic noncommunicable diseases, including CVDs. The introduction of standardised approaches to cardiovascular screening and assessment at the initial examination stage could reduce the time to diagnosis and improve the prognosis of patients.

The present work is devoted to the analysis of modern methods of detection of cardiovascular pathologies at the primary appointment with a therapist, as well as to the consideration of their significance in the system of prevention and early treatment.

The following methods were used in writing an article on the topic of detection of cardiovascular abnormalities at the initial examination by a therapist:

1. Literature analysis:
 - study of modern scientific publications, recommendations and guidelines on the diagnosis of cardiovascular diseases (CVD);
 - comparative analysis of domestic and international approaches to primary diagnosis;
 - study of data on the epidemiology of CVDs and their impact on mortality and quality of life.
2. Synthesising information:
 - Combining different sources of information to form a holistic view of the therapist's role in early detection of CVD;
 - Identification of key factors influencing the effectiveness of diagnosis, including instrumental and clinical methods.
3. Classification and systematisation:
 - grouping of examination methods (clinical, instrumental, laboratory);
 - classification of the main risk factors (age, gender, arterial hypertension, obesity, dyslipidaemia, etc.);
 - systematisation of the stages of the diagnostic process at the initial appointment.
4. Prediction method:
 - Evaluating the prospects of introducing new technologies and approaches (e.g. telemedicine, AI algorithms) to improve the detection of CVDs;
 - predicting the impact of improved early diagnosis on reducing mortality and morbidity.
5. Comparative method:
 - comparison of different methods of diagnostics of CVDs at the level of primary health care;
 - assessment of the effectiveness and availability of diagnostic methods in different settings (urban and rural medicine, countries with different levels of economic development).

The use of these methods made it possible to substantiate the importance and relevance of the topic, to struc-

ture the material, and to offer practical recommendations for improving the diagnosis of CVD at the primary stage.

thologies as ischaemic heart disease, arterial hypertension and heart failure can reduce the risk of complications, improve the quality of life of patients and reduce the costs of their treatment².

The key role in the early detection of CVD is assigned to primary care physicians, who are the first to encounter patients at the initial stages of the disease. This emphasises the need for effective diagnostic algorithms, including risk factor analysis, history taking, physical examination and the use of basic instrumental methods. In the context of increasing burden on health care systems, as well as increasing life expectancy of the population, the development and implementation of such approaches is of particular importance.

The main clinical manifestations of cardiovascular diseases (CVD) are presented in Table 1.

Cardiovascular diseases (CVDs) continue to occupy leading positions among the causes of mortality and morbidity at the global level. Their prevalence and severity of consequences make timely diagnosis not only a medical but also a social challenge. Early identification of such pa-

Table 1. Main clinical manifestations of cardiovascular diseases (CVD)

Category Patient complaints	<p>Clinical manifestations</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Chest pain: compressive, pressing, irradiating to the left arm, neck, back; provoked by exertion, relieved by nitrates. - Dyspnoea: on exertion or at rest, orthopnoea, nocturnal attacks of suffocation. - Heart palpitations: rapid, irregular, feeling of «freezing». - Swelling: on the lower extremities, increasing in the evening. - Dizziness and fainting: in hypotension or impaired cerebral circulation. - Increased fatigue: weakness as a sign of heart failure. - Hypertension ($\geq 140/90$ mmHg) or hypotension ($\leq 90/60$ mmHg). - BP difference between upper extremities. - Frequency: tachycardia (>100 beats/min), bradycardia (<60 beats/min). - Rhythm: irregular (sign of arrhythmia). - Filling and tension: weak, thready, strong. - Noises: systolic (e.g. aortic stenosis), diastolic (mitral insufficiency). - Weakening or strengthening of heart tones. - Additional sounds: third or fourth tone, pericardial friction murmur.
Auscultation of the lungs	- Wheezing, indicating stasis in the small circle of blood circulation.
Examination of the neck veins	- Venous swelling as a sign of increased central venous pressure.
Skin coverings	Skin coverings - Cyanosis (lips, nail beds), pallor, marbling of the skin.
Swelling and enlargement of the liver	- Swelling in the lower extremities, enlargement of the liver as a sign of blood stasis in the great circle of circulation.
Anthropometric data Peripheral arterial examination	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Obesity (body mass index), increased waist circumference (visceral obesity). - Weakened or absent pulse (atherosclerosis). - Noises above the arteries on auscultation.

Patient complaints are the main source of information at the initial examination stage. One of the most frequent symptoms of cardiovascular disease is chest pain characterised by a compressive, pressing or burning sensation³. Pain is usually localised behind the sternum or in the heart area, may irradiate to the left arm, neck, back and occurs against the background of physical activity or stress. It is often relieved at rest or after taking nitrates. Dyspnoea is also an important symptom. It can be manifested both during physical activity and at rest, intensify in the supine position, causing the need to assume an upright posture (orthopnoea). Nocturnal attacks of suffocation, known as cardiac asthma, indicate possible heart failure. Patients often complain of a rapid or irregular heartbeat accompanied by a feeling of “freezing” or “fluttering” in the chest, which may be associated with arrhythmias⁴. Swelling, mainly in the lower extremities, which increases in the evening, indicates fluid retention in the body, which is characteristic of circulatory disorders. Dizziness and fainting may be manifestations of hypotension, heart rhythm disturbances or insufficient blood supply to the brain. Increased fatigue and reduced exercise tolerance are frequent symptoms of chronic heart failure, reducing the patient’s quality of life⁵.

Blood pressure measurement is a mandatory part of the examination when cardiovascular disease is suspected. High blood pressure, or hypertension, is defined as values $\geq 140/90$ mmHg and is a major risk factor for cardiovascular complications. In contrast, hypotension, characterised by values $\leq 90/60$ mmHg, may accompany conditions with insufficient blood flow. The detection of a difference in blood pressure between the extremities allows to suspect vascular disorders such as coarctation of the aorta or peripheral arterial obstruction.

Assessment of the pulse rate provides information about the state of the cardiovascular system. The pulse rate may be elevated (tachycardia, more than 100 beats per minute) or decreased (bradycardia, less than 60 beats per minute). The above changes often reflect the functional state of the heart and possible pathological processes. Irregular pulse, for example, in the case of atrial fibrillation, indicates arrhythmias that require in-depth examination. Important characteristics of the pulse are its filling and tension. A weak or thready pulse may indicate a decreased cardiac output, whereas an increased pulse may indicate a hyperkinetic state⁶.

Cardiac auscultation is an important method of assessing the cardiovascular system. Noises detected on auscultation play a key role in diagnosis. Systolic murmurs may indicate conditions such as aortic stenosis or mitral regurgitation, while diastolic murmurs may be a sign of mitral stenosis or aortic insufficiency. Heart tones also have diagnostic value: a weakened first or second tone may indicate decreased heart muscle function or the presence of valve defects. Additional sounds, such as third and fourth tones or pericardial friction murmurs, are

signs of more specific conditions, including heart failure or pericardial inflammation.

At auscultation of lungs it is necessary to pay attention to the presence of moist rales, which may indicate congestion in the small circle of blood circulation. This is especially important when heart failure is suspected, as rales often accompany pulmonary oedema⁷.

Swelling of the neck veins is an important sign of increased central venous pressure. This symptom suggests right ventricular insufficiency or heart valve abnormalities such as tricuspid regurgitation.

Changes in the colour of the skin and visible mucous membranes may also indicate cardiovascular pathology. Cyanosis expressed on the lips and nail beds is a sign of hypoxia or insufficient oxygenation of the blood. Skin pallor may indicate anaemia or peripheral vasoconstriction, while skin marbling may indicate severe heart failure.

Swelling in the lower extremities, especially symmetrical, often indicates blood stasis in the great circulation. Liver enlargement, detected on palpation, is also associated with venous stasis and is a sign of severe heart failure.

The assessment of body mass index (BMI) and waist circumference is important for the detection of obesity, which is a key risk factor for cardiovascular disease. Increased waist circumference indicates visceral obesity, which is closely associated with metabolic syndrome and increased risk of atherosclerosis⁸.

Weakened or absent pulse in peripheral arteries, especially in the lower extremities, is a characteristic sign of atherosclerosis and vessel occlusion. Auscultation of the arteries may reveal murmurs that indicate turbulent blood flow and the presence of stenosis or aneurysm.

The initial diagnosis of cardiovascular disease (CVD) begins with a systematic approach that includes history taking, physical examination and the use of basic instrumental methods. The main aim of this stage is to identify suspected pathology requiring in-depth examination.

The first step is a thorough collection of anamnesis. The doctor analyses the patient’s complaints, paying special attention to chest pain, dyspnoea, oedema, palpitations and other symptoms that may be manifestations of coronary heart disease, arterial hypertension or heart failure. Risk factors are identified: family history, hypertension, diabetes, dyslipidaemia, smoking, obesity, sedentary lifestyle.

Physical examination is aimed at identifying objective signs of CVD. Blood pressure and pulse are measured, skin condition is assessed (cyanosis, marbling), heart and lung auscultation noises are detected. Palpation allows to assess the presence of oedema and liver enlargement, which is characteristic of heart failure.

Based on the collected data, the physician determines the need for instrumental studies, among which electrocardiography (ECG) plays a key role⁹.

ECG is an affordable, informative and non-invasive method that is used to diagnose most cardiovascular diseases. The ECG can detect:

- myocardial ischaemia and infarction: ST segment changes, inversion of the T plaque, abnormal Q plaques;
- rhythm and conduction disorders: arrhythmias, Hiss bundle branch block, atrial-ventricular block;
- hypertrophy of cardiac departments: thickening of the walls of the left or right ventricle;
- electrolyte disorders: changes in T and ST segment plaques associated with hypo- or hyperkalemia.

ECG is also an important method for monitoring disease dynamics and assessing the effectiveness of treatment.

The algorithm of primary diagnosis of cardiovascular diseases and the use of instrumental methods, such as electrocardiography (ECG), is based on a sequential approach that includes history taking, physical examination and, if necessary, instrumental studies for clarifying the diagnosis¹⁰.

The first stage of the algorithm is the collection of anamnesis. The doctor carefully listens to the patient, clarifying the nature of his complaints. It is important to identify chest pain, shortness of breath, oedema, heart rhythm disturbances and other symptoms that may indicate the presence of cardiovascular disease. The doctor looks for risk factors such as the presence of hypertension, diabetes, hypercholesterolemia, obesity, and a family history of heart and vascular disease. History taking helps the physician to form a preliminary idea of possible pathology, which is an important basis for further examination¹¹.

This is followed by a physical examination of the patient. This includes measurement of blood pressure and pulse rate. High blood pressure may indicate hypertension, and abnormal pulse rhythm may indicate arrhythmias. It is important to auscultate the heart and lungs for characteristic murmurs or wheezing, which may indicate valve disease or congestion in the lungs associated with heart failure. The patient's skin is also examined for cyanosis, pallor or marbling, which may be signs of hypoxia or circulatory failure. Palpation helps to detect swelling in the lower extremities and liver enlargement, which may indicate blood stasis and abnormalities in the great circle of blood circulation¹².

Based on the results of the physical examination, the doctor decides on the need for instrumental studies, one of which is electrocardiography (ECG). ECG is an important and accessible method of diagnosis, which is used to detect various heart rhythm disorders, myocardial ischaemia, infarction, hypertrophy of heart cham-

bers and electrolyte disorders. ECG allows the doctor to obtain information about the state of cardiac conduction and rhythm, as well as the presence of changes indicating myocardial damage or other pathologies.

The initial diagnosis is a standard resting ECG. In some cases, an exercise ECG (treadmill test) or daily ECG monitoring (Holter method) may be required to detect hidden arrhythmias or abnormalities that may not be apparent at rest. The data obtained is carefully analysed by the doctor to detect abnormalities. It is important that the physician correctly interprets ECG changes: inversion of the T, ST-segment elevation or ST-segment depression may indicate myocardial ischaemia, the presence of an abnormal Q-sign may indicate a previous heart attack, and rhythm disturbances may indicate arrhythmias such as atrial fibrillation or ventricular tachycardia¹³.

Once the ECG results are obtained, the physician will assess the need for further diagnostic procedures. If the ECG shows changes that require more detailed examination, the patient may be referred for additional tests such as echocardiography (cardiac ultrasound) to assess the structure and function of the heart, stress tests to assess the heart's response to exercise, or angiography to examine blood vessels and detect atherosclerotic changes.

Thus, the algorithm of primary diagnosis of cardiovascular diseases consists of a consistent collection of anamnesis, physical examination and the use of instrumental diagnostic methods, such as ECG. Early detection of changes allows the doctor to accurately diagnose and timely prescribe appropriate treatment.

Discussion. Key risk factors for cardiovascular diseases (CVDs) play a crucial role in the development and progression of these diseases. Among them, hypertension, dyslipidaemia, obesity and diabetes mellitus are the main ones. Each of these conditions significantly increases the likelihood of CVDs and, in particular, severe diseases such as coronary heart disease, stroke, heart failure and atherosclerosis.

Hypertension is one of the most common diseases characterised by a persistent increase in blood pressure. Hypertension is a major risk factor for myocardial infarctions, strokes and chronic heart failure. Increased pressure puts additional strain on the heart and blood vessels, which over time can lead to wear and tear and the development of atherosclerosis. Controlling blood pressure with antihypertensive medications and lifestyle changes such as reducing salt intake, increasing physical activity and weight management can reduce the risk of serious complications¹⁴.

Dyslipidaemia is a lipid metabolism disorder that includes elevated levels of low-density cholesterol (LDL) and triglycerides in the blood, and low levels of high-density cholesterol (HDL). High levels of LDL, or "bad" cholesterol, contribute to the formation of atherosclerotic plaques on the walls of arteries, causing them to narrow and im-

pair blood flow. This can cause myocardial infarctions and strokes. Management of dyslipidaemia includes the prescription of statins and other drugs aimed at normalising cholesterol levels, as well as lifestyle correction: reducing saturated fat intake, increasing physical activity, body weight control and smoking cessation¹⁵.

Obesity is a condition in which excessive accumulation of adipose tissue disrupts the normal functioning of the body. Obesity is an important risk factor for the development of hypertension, diabetes, dyslipidaemia and cardiovascular disease. Excess weight increases the workload on the heart, contributes to high blood pressure and metabolic disorders. Obesity management includes dietary changes, increased physical activity and, in some cases, medication or surgery to achieve normalisation of body weight.

Diabetes mellitus is a disease characterised by high blood sugar levels, which can be caused by insufficient insulin production or by the body's impaired response to this hormone. Diabetes contributes to the development of atherosclerosis and deterioration of blood vessels, which increases the risk of strokes, heart attacks and heart failure. Controlling blood glucose levels, diet, physical activity and the use of antidiabetic medications can help prevent or slow the development of diabetes-related complications¹⁶.

A preventive approach is key to reducing morbidity and mortality from cardiovascular disease. The importance of prevention lies in the fact that CVDs often develop slowly and do not have pronounced symptoms in the early stages. The use of preventive measures can significantly reduce the risk of their development. The main preventive strategies include:

Blood pressure control - regular monitoring and maintenance of normal blood pressure levels help prevent the development of hypertension and its associated complications¹⁷.

Cholesterol and lipid control - eating a healthy diet that includes healthy fats (omega-3), reducing saturated fat intake and avoiding trans fats can help maintain normal cholesterol levels.

Physical activity - regular exercise (at least 150 minutes of moderate exercise per week) helps to normalise weight and improve vascular and heart health.

Weight management - maintaining a normal weight helps to reduce the strain on the heart and blood vessels and improve metabolism.

Smoking cessation - smoking is an important risk factor for atherosclerosis and impairs blood supply to the heart muscle.

Controlling blood sugar levels - regular monitoring and keeping glucose levels normal is important to prevent diabetic complications.

Psycho-emotional state - reducing stress levels and avoiding chronic nervous overload is also an important element of prevention, as stress contributes to high blood pressure and metabolic disturbances¹⁸.

Thus, a preventive approach requires a comprehensive approach that includes control of key risk factors, lifestyle changes and, if necessary, drug treatment. Timely diagnosis and correction of these factors can significantly reduce the likelihood of cardiovascular disease and improve the quality of life.

The role of the therapist in early detection of cardiovascular disease (CVD) and referral to a cardiologist is key to early diagnosis and prevention of complications such as myocardial infarction, stroke, heart failure and other life-threatening conditions. The therapist is often the first doctor to whom a patient presents with symptoms that may indicate cardiovascular problems. In this context, his or her role is not only to perform initial diagnostics, but also to refer the patient to specialised specialists in a timely manner for in-depth examination and treatment.

The therapist is the first link in the chain of diagnosis of cardiovascular disease. At the initial appointment, the doctor should take a careful history, including chest pain, shortness of breath, dizziness, oedema and abnormal heart rhythm. These symptoms may indicate conditions that require specialised treatment, such as coronary heart disease, arterial hypertension, heart rhythm disorders or valve disease.

Based on clinical examination and measurements of blood pressure, pulse, and auscultation of the heart and lungs, the general practitioner may suspect the presence of serious diseases such as hypertension, heart failure, atherosclerosis and other pathologies. It is important that the physician recognises the first signs of these diseases and promptly refers the patient to a cardiologist, who can perform an in-depth examination and prescribe appropriate treatment.

The therapist also plays an important role in identifying and controlling risk factors such as hypertension, dyslipidaemia, obesity, diabetes mellitus and smoking. These factors significantly increase the likelihood of developing cardiovascular disease. The therapist should regularly monitor the patient's health status, measure blood pressure, check cholesterol and blood sugar levels, and assess body weight and other indicators of cardiovascular risk¹⁹.

If the general practitioner identifies abnormalities such as hypertension, high cholesterol or diabetes, he or she should not only suggest therapeutic measures to control these conditions but also refer the patient to a cardiologist for a more detailed examination and individualised therapy. It is important that the general practitioner is actively involved in the prevention and treatment process, monitoring risk factors and, if necessary, referring the patient to a more specialised consultation for further correction.

Timely referral to a cardiologist has several important advantages. A cardiologist with specialised knowledge and experience is able to detect diseases at earlier stages, when treatment can be more effective. He or she can also prescribe individualised therapy, taking into account the specifics of the disease and the patient's condition, which can significantly increase the effectiveness of treatment and reduce the risk of complications.

Timely treatment and control of diseases such as hypertension or ischaemic heart disease can prevent the development of serious complications such as myocardial infarction or stroke. The cardiologist can adjust therapy if necessary, combining drug therapy with rehabilitation measures, physical activity and lifestyle changes²⁰.

The therapist should refer the patient to a cardiologist in the following cases:

- suspicion of cardiovascular disease - in the presence of chest pain, dyspnoea, arrhythmia, dizziness or fainting;
- treatment failure - if standard therapies for hypertension, dyslipidaemia or other diseases are not effective;
- Identification of high risk factors - such as severe hypertension, severe dyslipidaemia, diabetes mellitus, obesity or hereditary predisposition;
- the need for an in-depth examination - in the presence of abnormal ECG, echocardiography or other findings that require interpretation by a specialist.

Another important role of the therapist is to prevent cardiovascular disease through patient education. The GP should inform the patient about the importance of controlling risk factors, such as maintaining normal blood pressure, cholesterol and blood sugar levels, as well as the need for a healthy diet, regular physical activity, smoking cessation and maintaining a healthy weight. This will help patients to reduce their risk of developing CVDs and improve their quality of life.

Thus, the therapist plays a central role in primary diagnosis, prevention and timely referral of patients to a cardiologist. Early detection and control of risk factors, as well as active referral of the patient for consultation with a subspecialist, allow not only to improve prognosis, but also to prevent the development of severe cardiovascular diseases and their complications²¹.

The need to integrate a comprehensive approach to the detection of cardiovascular diseases (CVDs) in the practice of primary care physicians is becoming increasingly important in light of the high morbidity and mortality rates from these diseases. Cardiovascular disease remains one of the leading causes of death and disability worldwide, and early diagnosis, prevention, and comprehensive and consistent treatment play a key role in reducing its impact on public health.

An integrated approach involves the use of various diagnostic methods, risk factor assessment and preventive measures for the timely detection of cardiovascular diseases at early stages. It is important that primary care physicians, such as therapists, not only perform basic diagnostics, but also timely refer patients to subspecialists for in-depth examinations, if necessary.

A comprehensive approach involves several key aspects. The primary care physician should listen carefully to the patient, identify symptoms that may indicate possible cardiovascular disease, and collect information about risk factors such as hypertension, diabetes mellitus, dyslipidaemia, obesity, smoking and others. Knowing these factors allows the physician to predict possible cardiovascular problems in advance and take steps to prevent or control them²².

At the primary level, the physician should actively use available diagnostic methods to detect signs of CVD. These may include blood pressure measurements to detect hypertension, ECGs to monitor heart function, blood tests for cholesterol and sugar levels to determine the presence of dyslipidaemia and diabetes mellitus. These tests are affordable and easy to perform but can provide important information for early detection of pathology.

The primary care physician must be able to interpret even minor changes in a patient's condition, such as palpitations, shortness of breath, chest pain, oedema or dizziness. Sometimes these symptoms may be early signs of more serious conditions that require specialised treatment. Even in the absence of significant symptoms, it is important to monitor trends in the patient's health to help prevent the development of severe forms of the disease.

The primary care physician is obliged to carry out active preventive work with patients, teaching them the importance of controlling risk factors. Regular monitoring of health status, prescription of diet, physical activity and other measures helps to prevent the development of diseases such as arterial hypertension, coronary heart disease, atherosclerosis and others²³.

Despite the therapist's best efforts in primary diagnosis and prevention, some cases require more in-depth examination and a specialised approach. Primary care physicians play an important role in timely referral of patients to cardiologists for in-depth examination. For example, if ECG or other test results indicate heart rhythm abnormalities, myocardial hypertrophy or other abnormalities, this may signal the need for a more accurate diagnosis and appropriate treatment. The cardiologist, in turn, may use more sophisticated diagnostic techniques such as echocardiography, stress tests, angiography, and prescribe individualised treatment.

Physicians should be well prepared for the early detection of risk factors and heart disease, as well as for the use of modern diagnostic methods. This includes regular updating of knowledge about new prevention and treat-

ment methods, as well as learning to better interpret clinical and laboratory data.

Modern electronic systems can help physicians track patient data in dynamics, analyse disease history, and predict possible risks. These technologies make it easier for primary care physicians to notice changes in a patient's health status and refer him or her for a specialised examination in a timely manner²⁴.

It is important that general practitioners, cardiologists and other specialists communicate effectively to share information and work together to diagnose and treat patients. Creating teamwork between different levels of care helps to improve quality of care and outcomes.

Integration of a comprehensive approach to the detection of cardiovascular diseases in the practice of a primary care physician is a prerequisite for improving the efficiency of diagnosis and reducing mortality from these diseases. Timely identification of risk factors, regular monitoring of the patient's condition, use of available instrumental methods and active preventive work can significantly improve the prognosis for patients and reduce the burden of CVDs at the public health level²⁵.

In recent years, there has been a rapid development of new technologies in medicine, and their introduction into primary care has the potential to significantly improve the detection of cardiovascular disease (CVD), speed up diagnosis and increase the effectiveness of prevention. Among such technologies, telemedicine and artificial intelligence (AI) are already finding practical application and promise to revolutionise approaches to diagnostics.

Telemedicine is the use of information and communication technologies to deliver health services at a distance. This may include remote consultations, monitoring the health status of patients with chronic diseases and transferring medical data between doctors.

AI and machine learning algorithms are becoming an important tool in the field of disease diagnosis. In particular, they can be used for analysing medical data and big data diagnostics. AI algorithms can effectively analyse large data sets from ECGs, blood tests, ultrasounds and other examination methods and identify patterns that may not be obvious to a doctor, which can help in the early diagnosis of cardiovascular diseases.

AI can be used to create models that will predict the risk of developing diseases, such as myocardial infarction or stroke, based on data about risk factors, genetic predisposition, lifestyle and other factors. AI can help automate some diagnostic procedures, such as interpreting ECGs or analysing ultrasound images, to speed up diagnosis and reduce errors.

AI systems require significant effort to learn and adapt correctly to a variety of medical data. Physicians must be trained to use such technologies and interpret the results

correctly. The effectiveness of AI is highly dependent on the quality of the input data. Incorrectly collected or insufficiently high quality data can lead to misdiagnoses.

Improved early diagnosis and effective use of new technologies can have a significant impact on reducing cardiovascular mortality and morbidity²⁶.

Improvements in early diagnosis and prevention can significantly reduce the cost of treating late-stage diseases such as myocardial infarction or stroke. Preventive treatment and early intervention reduce the need for costly surgeries and hospitalisations, thus saving money for both the patient and the health care system. The introduction of new technologies, such as telemedicine and AI, into primary care practices holds great promise for improving the diagnosis and prevention of cardiovascular disease. These technologies can significantly increase the availability of medical services, speed up diagnosis and improve treatment outcomes²⁷. In turn, effective early diagnosis and prevention can significantly reduce morbidity and mortality from CVDs, improve the quality of life of patients and reduce the economic costs of treatment of late-stage diseases.

Conclusions

CVDs remain one of the major causes of premature death and disability globally. These diseases tend to be asymptomatic in their early stages, emphasising the importance of timely diagnosis and prevention at the earliest stages. The therapist plays a key role in the primary diagnosis and prevention of cardiovascular disease. It is at the initial appointment, the doctor collects anamnesis, conducts physical examination, assesses risk factors and prescribes the necessary studies. Early detection and correction of risk factors such as hypertension, dyslipidaemia, obesity, diabetes mellitus and smoking significantly reduce the probability of CVD development.

Effective detection of cardiovascular diseases at the primary level requires a comprehensive approach, including history taking, assessment of risk factors, physical examination, use of instrumental methods (e.g. blood pressure measurement, ECG, blood tests). This allows timely suspicion of pathologies requiring specialised examination and treatment.

It is important that the therapist is able to recognise the signs of more serious conditions and refer the patient to a cardiologist if necessary. Early referral to a specialist allows for an in-depth examination and treatment before serious complications such as myocardial infarction or stroke develop.

Prevention of cardiovascular diseases is a key task at the primary health care level. Teaching patients to adopt

a healthy lifestyle, including a healthy diet, regular physical activity, smoking cessation and body weight control, helps to significantly reduce the risk of heart and vascular diseases. To improve the efficiency of diagnostics and treatment of CVDs, it is necessary to integrate a comprehensive approach into the practice of primary care physicians, which includes the use of modern medical technologies, training of physicians, and the development of co-operation between general practitioners and subspecialists, which helps to improve the quality of diagnostics and treatment.

A comprehensive and early approach to the diagnosis and treatment of CVDs at the primary health care level contributes to the reduction of morbidity and mortality, as well as reducing the burden on secondary and tertiary health care. Cardiovascular disease is an important societal problem requiring effective strategies for early diagnosis and prevention. The therapist, as the first point of contact with the health care system, plays a critical role in identifying patients at risk of developing CVD. Integration of a comprehensive approach into the practice of the primary care physician, as well as active prevention, monitoring of risk factors and timely referral to cardiologists can significantly reduce mortality and morbidity from cardiovascular disease, which will ultimately improve the health of the population and increase the effectiveness of the health care system as a whole.

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